

Twisted Molecular Nanoribbons with up to 53 Linearly-Fused Rings

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ABSTRACT: The synthesis of three molecular nanoribbons with a twisted aromatic framework is described. The largest one shows a 53 linearly-fused rings backbone (12.9 nm) and 322 conjugated atoms in its aromatic core (C₂₉₆N₂₄S₂). This new family of nanoribbons show extremely high molar absorptivities, reaching 986100 M⁻¹cm⁻¹, and red-emitting properties.

INTRODUCTION

In the last decades, chemists have devoted significant efforts to the synthesis of increasingly larger molecular structures to push the boundaries of the molecular world into the nanoscale. Among these structures, nanographenes¹⁻⁸ –polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons that extend over 1 nm– are receiving increasing attention not only as synthetic challenges, but also because of their precise and highly tunable properties with a lot of potential in electronic, spintronic, photonic, photodetector and energy conversion applications. Even if the synthesis of giant nanographenes (those with approximately >150 conjugated atoms in their aromatic core) constantly defy our synthetic abilities, several giant nanographenes –such as C₁₃₈N₆,⁹ C₁₅₀,^{10, 11} C₁₅₃,¹² C₁₄₄N₂₄,¹³ C₁₇₀,¹⁴ C₁₈₆,¹⁵ C₁₉₈,¹⁶ C₁₈₆N₃₀,¹⁷ C₂₁₆,¹⁸ C₂₂₂,^{19, 20} and C₂₅₈,²¹ have been reported, among which, C₂₅₈²¹ is the largest nanographene reported to this day. Several of these giant nanographenes show either a twisted aromatic core^{9-11, 15, 16, 20, 21} or a complex equilibrium between multiple twisted conformers.^{13, 17} These planarity distortions, generated by the introduction of strain in key positions, endow the nanographenes with a high solubility that allow their characterization by a broad range of techniques, which is very challenging for planar systems of the same size.

In this context, graphene nanoribbons (NRs)^{2, 3, 5, 7, 22-29} – nanographenes that extend in one-dimension– have attracted a lot of interest because their structure dominates their optical, electronic, electrical and magnetic properties, providing a unique platform to develop new materials. For instance, the edge structure controls their metallicity and magnetic properties, while the width, length and heteroatom-doping control their energy levels, and therefore, their band gaps and their optoelectronic and redox properties. This illustrates that the synthesis of molecular (or monodisperse) NRs is key to establish their fundamental properties and exploit their potential. Among the different top-down^{22, 30} and bottom-up^{2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 22-28, 30, 31} approaches to prepare NRs, only organic synthesis can provide atomic precision simultaneously over edge, width, length and

heteroatom-doping. Yet, organic synthesis remains a challenging approach to prepare molecular NRs as the increasingly longer synthetic routes for increasingly larger NRs are often beset by incomplete transformations, and insoluble intermediates and final products, which make difficult and even hamper in some cases purification and characterization. Nevertheless, organic synthesis has provided an impressive wealth of different families of molecular NRs that extend over 2 nm in length,^{2, 11, 13, 24, 26, 32-49} and that evolve from acene, pyrene, perylene, and coronene derivatives, among which C₁₄₄N₂₄¹³ is the longest with a 30 linearly-fused rings backbone of 7.7 nm.

In this work, we describe the synthesis of three molecular NRs with a 13, 33, and 53 linearly-fused rings backbone (respectively, **NR-13**, **NR-33** and **NR-53**, Figure 1a-c), which belong to a new family of NRs with an alternating cove-cape zigzag edge and a twisted aromatic framework. The lengths of **NR-33** (8.0 nm) and **NR-53** (12.9 nm) surpass, and in the case of **NR-53** almost doubles, the current length record. In addition, **NR-53** with 322 conjugated atoms (C₂₉₆N₂₄S₂) in the aromatic core (highlighted in gray in Figure 1) sets also a new record as the largest synthetic nanographene. Remarkably, **NR-13**, **NR-33** and **NR-53** show very high solubility in common organic solvents at room temperature as the result of their twisted aromatic framework and of the carefully selected and placed solubilizing groups. This high solubility allowed the purification of the NRs by column chromatography and their characterization by a broad range of structural, optoelectronic and redox characterization techniques, which allowed establishing unambiguously their structure and their fundamental properties. For instance, this new family of NRs show extremely high molar absorptivities >10⁵ M⁻¹cm⁻¹, reaching 986100 M⁻¹cm⁻¹ in the case of **NR-53**. And also, despite their dimensions, **NR-13**, **NR-33** and **NR-53** show a red fluorescence.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Design and synthesis. **NR-13**, **NR-33** and **NR-53** show a cove-cape zigzag edge obtained by fusion of perylene, pyrene and pyrazino- or thiazolo-quinoxaline residues. They

Figure 1. Chemical structure of a) NR-13, b) NR-33 and c) NR-53. The lettering indicates the proton assignments on the 1H NMR spectra in this figure and in the supporting information. The molecular formula indicates only the number of atoms in the aromatic core (highlighted in gray). d) Front view and e), f) side views of the crystal structure of NR-13, in which solubilizing groups have been removed for clarity. g) Partial 1H NMR spectra of NR-13, NR-33 and NR-53 in $CDCl_3$ at room temperature.

were obtained by combining different sets of building blocks (A-E) equipped with terminal *o*-quinone or *o*-diamine functionalities (Scheme 1a). These functionalities have been selected in order to fuse together the building blocks, because *o*-quinones and *o*-diamines converge through the formation of a pyrazine ring by an imine-type cyclocondensation reaction. Given the size of the NRs, a careful optimization of the reaction conditions was carried out to achieve maximum selectivity and yields and to avoid the use of protective groups. 1-Hexylheptyl, *tert*-butyl and tri-*iso*-butylsilyl substituents were carefully selected and placed respectively on the precursors of the corresponding perylene, pyrene and (pyrazino or thidiazolo)quinoxaline residues to ensure the solubility of the intermediates and of the final NRs.

The starting point for the synthesis of the NRs is compound **1** (Scheme 1a), which was obtained in three steps from perylenetetracarboxylic dianhydride by modifying a reported route⁵⁰ in order to introduce the desired 1-hexylheptyl solubilizing groups (Scheme S1). The pyrene residues of compound **1** were oxidized using NaIO₄ in the presence of RuCl₃ to yield **A** (10%) with two *o*-quinones on the K-region of the terminal pyrene residues. Subsequently, precursor **A** was condensed with 1.2 equivalents of **B**¹³ to yield the monocondensation product **C** (52%). The cyclocondensation of **C** with an excess of tetraaminobenzene **2**, provided intermediate **3** (58%), which was then condensed with an excess of **A** to provide **D** (69%). The

condensation of **A** with an excess of tetraaminobenzene **2** yielded the dicondensed block **E** (29%). Finally, **NR-13** (76%), **NR-33** (73%) and **NR-53** (66%) were obtained by a double condensation of **A**, **E** and **E** respectively with **B**, **C** and **D** (Scheme 1b-d). The NRs are significantly stable, showing no signs of decomposition after several months in ambient conditions.

Structural characterization. Remarkably, despite their large conjugated aromatic frameworks and molecular weights, **NR-13** (2586.03 Da), **NR-33** (6479.85 Da), and **NR-53** (10373.66 Da) exhibited a high solubility in common organic solvents, such as CHCl₃, CH₂Cl₂, toluene, and THF (Table S1). This high solubility allowed their purification by column chromatography and also NMR characterization in CDCl₃ at room temperature in all cases. The structure of the NRs was unambiguously confirmed ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy, and matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS). The ¹H NMR spectra of NRs showed peaks and integrations consistent with their structure and symmetry (Figure 1e). **NR-13** show two signals that correspond to the eight protons on the pyrene residues (P1 and P2) and a signal that correspond to the overlap of two non-equivalent protons (C1) on the coronene residue (a coronene is obtained upon the fusion of perylene with two pyrenes) as a result of the *N*-alkyl substitution. In **NR-33**, six signals were observed for the twenty-four protons sitting on the

Scheme 1. Synthetic routes for a) building blocks A-E, b) NR-13, c) NR-33 and d) NR-53.

pyrene residues (P1-P6) and twelve protons (C1 and C2) on the coronene residue overlapped on the same region. For **NR-53**, six signals were observed for the forty protons sitting on the pyrene residues (P1-P6) and twenty coronene protons (C1-C3) overlapped on the same region. These assignments are consistent with the integration of the signals in the aliphatic region (Figure S1), where the number of signals and integration increases proportionally to the larger number of 1-hexylheptyl, *tert*-butyl and tri-*iso*-butylsilyl groups with the increasing NR dimensions. The structure of the NRs was further confirmed by MALDI-TOF MS that showed molecular ion peaks and isotopic distributions consistent with their molecular weights (Figure S2).

We attempted to grow single crystals for the whole NR series, which was very challenging given their large molecular weights and the high number and flexibility of the solubilizing groups. To our delight, we succeeded to obtain crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction in the case of **NR-13**, by slow diffusion of methanol vapors into a solution of **NR-13** in chloroform. The single crystal X-ray structure of **NR-13** evidence its twisted aromatic core at the coronene-pyrene junctions. These twists are the result of steric congestion between the hydrogens located at the cove regions (Figure 1d), which force the coronene residue to twist away 34° from the NR main plane. In addition, the X-ray structure evidence that the thiadiazoloquinoline residues are slightly bent out-of-the-plane in opposite directions.

Structural analysis and electronic structure. The crystal structure of **NR-13** together with tight-binding (GFN2-xTB) refined with DFT (B3LYP/6-31G(d,p)) computer models allowed to gain insight into the structure of the higher NRs, since **NR-13** is a common residue in **NR-33** and **NR-53**. For computational efficiency, after a comparative validation against **NR13**, calculations were carried out on **NR-13-H**, **NR-33-H** and **NR-53-H** (Figure S3), in which the solubilizing groups have been substituted by hydrogen atoms. In all the three cases the most likely structures found (lowest strain) present the same twisted structure in the pyrene-perylene junction observed in the crystal structure of **NR-13**, namely a flat NR core with the perylene residues twisting out of the plane in an alternated fashion. The end-to-end (S-to-S) distances were 3.14, 8.03 and 12.91 nm respectively for **NR-13**, **NR-33** and **NR-53**. The conformational analysis⁵¹ of **NR-13-H** evidenced different twisted conformations, such as alternated (achiral), helical (chiral), boat (chiral) and double-boat (achiral) conformations (Figure S4). The lowest energy conformation corresponds to the alternated conformation observed on the crystal structure. Nevertheless, all conformations were found to be energetically accessible at room temperature (Figure S5) and therefore in constant exchange. This constant conformational exchange also contributes to the high solubility observed on the NRs.

Bond length analysis, nuclear independent chemical shifts (NICS(0)) and anisotropy of the induced current density (ACID) plots provide fundamental information about the electronic structure of the NRs (Figure 2a-b). The bond lengths observed on the crystal structure of **NR-13** are in good agreement with the calculated ones, which validates the predictions for **NR-33** and **NR-53**. On the basis of the bond length alternation and the NICS(0) values (Figures 2a and S6), the dominant resonance structure is best represented by a coronene group (3 sextets) in the coronene residues, a biphenyl groups (2 sextets) in the pyrene residues, and an anthracene group (1 sextet) in the pyrazo- and thiadiazoloquinoline residues (Figures 1a-c). For

instance, negative NICS(0) values were found on almost all the rings of the pyrene, coronene and pyrazo- or thiadiazoloquinoline residues (shown in red), but on the linearly-annulated pyrene rings and on the central coronene rings, which show positive and nearly positive values (shown in blue). The anisotropy of the induced current density (ACID) plots of **NR-13**, **NR-33** and **NR-53** (Figure 2b and S7) are also consistent with this assignment, showing a diamagnetic current that goes around the NR periphery (red trace).

Optoelectronic and redox properties. The NR powders showed an intense purple coloration in all cases, but slightly lighter in the case of **NR-13**. However, in solution, the different NRs show different colors (**NR-13** is purple, **NR-33** is gray, and **NR-53** is dark gray) as evidenced by comparing equimolar (5 μ M) chloroform solutions (Figure 2c). The same solutions show a similar red emission that becomes more intense with the increasing length of the NRs (Figure 2d).

The UV-vis electronic absorption spectra of the three NRs exhibit similar absorption patterns, in which three major bands at ca. 405, 480 and 600 nm dominate the spectra (Figure 2e and Table S2), which were assigned to the β , α , and ρ bands,⁵² respectively. The ρ bands appear increasingly red-shifted with the increasing length of the NR ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 595, 608$ and 610 nm, respectively for **NR-13**, **NR-33** and **NR-53**). Very large molar absorptivities ($\epsilon > 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$) were observed in all cases, which increase with the increasing size of the NR, as illustrated by the ϵ values of the β bands (250100, 589500 and 986100 $\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$, respectively, for **NR-13**, **NR-33** and **NR-53**). **NR-53** shows an extremely high ϵ value (986100 $\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$), which surpasses the largest values reported for a single nanographene chromophore (844000 $\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ for C_{186} ¹⁵). **NR-33** and **NR-53** show respectively molar absorptivities $> 0.5 \times 10^5$ and $> 0.8 \times 10^5$ across the whole visible spectrum up to 630 nm, which explains their gray coloration (Figure 2c). Such large and broad molar absorptivities in the visible are highly desirable for photovoltaic and photodetector applications.⁵³⁻⁵⁵ The experimental HOMO-LUMO gap (E_{gap}) values (2.00, 1.98 and 1.97 eV respectively for **NR-13**, **NR-33** and **NR-53**) were estimated from the onset of the lowest energy absorption bands (Table S2). The E_{gap} values are almost the same, independently of the length of the NR, which illustrates that the energy gap saturates rapidly for this type of multi-edge NRs. This behavior is consistent with a the calculated E_{gap} values (see below) and also with other narrow NRs in which E_{gap} saturates after surpassing 10 linearly-fused rings.^{13, 56} The E_{gap} values are in a similar range of well-established semiconductors, such as BP, AlAs, AlSb, Cu_2O , GaSe, 3C-SiC, and SnS_2 .

The emission spectra of **NR-13**, **NR-33** and **NR-53** show fluorescence bands that extend from the red into the near infrared (NIR) region and that become narrower as the length of the NRs increase (Figure 2f and Table S2). The emission maxima of **NR-33** and **NR-53**, at 623 nm in both cases, appear bathochromically shifted (3 nm) in comparison to that of **NR-13**. The small fluorescence wavelength shifts in comparison to those observed on the absorption spectra were attributed to a less intense 0-0 transition in the case of **NR-13**, which shows a shoulder at a slightly higher energy from the peak maximum. In contrast to most soluble giant nanographenes, which generally show weak or no fluorescence,^{9, 10, 14, 16, 20, 21} the fluorescence quantum yields of **NR-13**, **NR-33** and **NR-53** show values of 0.12, 0.20 and 0.22, respectively. The quantum yield value of **NR-53** is

Figure 2. a) Bond length analysis and NICS(0) values of **NR-53-H**. Bonds are rendered in a color continuum ranging from red (1.31 Å) to white (1.40 Å) to blue (1.49 Å) so that Clar's aromatic sextets are lighter/whiter colors and localized double and single bonds are red and blue, respectively. b) ACID plots of **NR-53-H**. Solutions of **NR-13**, **NR-33** and **NR-53** in CHCl_3 (5 μM) under c) natural light and d) UV light. e) Absorption and f) fluorescence spectra in CHCl_3 and g) cyclic voltammograms in $n\text{-Bu}_4\text{NPF}_6/\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ (20 mV/s) of **NR-13**, **NR-33** and **NR-53**. h) Representative B3LYP-6-31G(d,p)- CHCl_3 /B3LYP frontier orbitals for **NR-53-H**.

remarkably high considering the size of its aromatic core. These quantum yield values may be caused by the high solubility of this family of NRs and of their longitudinally twisted backbone that do not infer a π -overlap between different parts of the aromatic core. For instance, such π -overlaps, which are known to quench the fluorescence in helicenes,⁵⁷ are a common motif in weakly emitting giant nanographenes.^{9, 10, 16, 21} This rationale is also consistent with the high emissive properties observed on some giant aromatics that do not show π -overlaps in their twisted aromatic core.^{11-13, 17, 49}

The redox properties of the NRs were studied by cyclic voltammetry in a N_2 saturated solution of $n\text{-Bu}_4\text{NPF}_6$ in anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 (0.1 M) as the supporting electrolyte and with ferrocene (Fc) as an internal standard. All the three NRs exhibited three reductions waves (Figure 2g and Table S2) and no oxidations within the solvent-supported electrolyte potential window. The

reduction half-wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) of the NRs were very similar ($E_{1/2}^{\text{NR-13}} = -1.02, -1.40$ and -1.66 V, $E_{1/2}^{\text{NR-33}} = -1.01, -1.37$ and -1.60 V, $E_{1/2}^{\text{NR-53}} = -0.98, -1.38$ and -1.63 V vs Fc/Fc^+) and confirm that all the NRs are electron-deficient materials. The electrochemical LUMO or electron affinities (E_{LUMO}) were estimated from the onset potential of the first reduction wave of the cyclic voltammograms. The E_{LUMO} values ($-3.88, -3.88$ and -3.87 eV, respectively for **NR-13**, **NR-33** and **NR-53**) are virtually unaffected by the size of the NRs.

To shine additional light on the optoelectrochemical and redox properties, DFT calculations (B3LYP-6-311+G(d,p)- CH_2Cl_2 /B3LYP-6-31G(d,p)) were carried out on **NR-13-H**, **NR-33-H** and **NR-53-H**. TD-DFT revealed that the ρ band in the case of **NR-13-H** corresponds to a HOMO \rightarrow LUMO transition (Table S3). While in the case of **NR-33-H** and **NR-53-H**, the ρ bands correspond to all the transitions between the

quasidegenerate HOMOs (3 and 5 quasidegenerate HOMO orbitals respectively for **NR-33-H** and **NR-53-H**) and the degenerate LUMOs (2 quasidegenerate LUMO orbitals for both **NR-33-H** and **NR-53-H**) (Figures 2h and S8-S10, Table S3). The LUMO and LUMO+1 are localized on the pyrazinobenzothiadiazole ends in all cases, while the different quasidegenerate HOMOs are spread across different pyrene-perylene-pyrene residues of the NR framework (representative HOMO, LUMO and LUMO+1 of **NR-53** are shown on Figure 2h). The computed E_{gap} (1.97, 1.90, and 1.89 eV, respectively for **NR-13-H**, **NR-33-H** and **NR-53-H**) show similar values and the same decreasing trend as the experimental ones, which indicates that the gap has not yet saturated. The computed E_{LUMO} (-3.85, -3.84, -3.83 eV, respectively for **NR-13-H**, **NR-33-H** and **NR-53-H**) also correlate very well with the experimental ones and show nearly invariable values. The similar E_{LUMO} in all NRs is consistent with the localization of the LUMOs on the pyrazinobenzothiadiazole ends in all the NR series (Figure 2h and S8-S10).

CONCLUSION

We have reported the synthesis of a new family of molecular NRs that reach dimensions (12.9 nm in length and 322 conjugated atoms in the aromatic core) that exceed both the largest lengths reported for molecular NRs (7.7 nm)¹³ and the largest aromatic cores reported for nanographenes (258 conjugated atoms).²¹ This family of NRs show a cape-cove zigzag edge as the result of the fusion of perylene, pyrene and (thiadiazolo- or pyrazo-)quinoxalines. The steric congestion at the coronene and pyrene junctions induces a twisted geometry as evidenced by X-ray crystallography and theoretical calculations. The twisted aromatic framework, together with the presence of carefully selected solubilizing groups, resulted in an excellent solubility in common organic solvents at room temperature, which allowed their purification by column chromatography, and also, a broad characterization by ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy, MS, UV-vis absorption and fluorescence spectroscopy, and cyclic voltammetry. Optoelectronic characterization evidence the remarkable light absorbing capabilities of the NRs that show molar absorptivities that increase with the length with extremely high values up to 986100 M⁻¹cm⁻¹, which surpass the largest values reported for a single nanographene chromophore.¹⁵ Furthermore, red-emitting properties have been observed in all the NRs. Electrochemical characterization evidence that these are electron-deficient NRs with length-independent LUMO energies as the result of LUMO localization at the NR's ends. Overall, this work provides new design strategies for the synthesis of giant molecular NRs and nanographenes which are processible in solution and possess remarkable optoelectronic properties.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website.

Experimental details of the synthesis, characterization and calculations. Crystallographic data for **NR-13** (2061916) are also deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre.

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The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. / All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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ABBREVIATIONS

NR, nanoribbon; NMR, nuclear magnetic resonance; MALDI-TOF MS, matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry; NICS, nuclear independent chemical shifts; ACID, anisotropy of the induced current density; NIR, near infrared; DFT, density functional theory; HOMO, highest occupied molecular orbital; LUMO, lowest unoccupied molecular orbital.

REFERENCES

1. Narita, A., Synthesis of Structurally Defined Nanographene Materials through Oxidative Cyclodehydrogenation. In *Synthetic Methods for Conjugated Polymers and Carbon Materials*, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA: Weinheim, 2017; pp 183-228.
2. Mateo-Alonso, A., Pyrene-fused pyrazaacenes: from small molecules to nanoribbons. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2014**, *43* (17), 6311-6324.
3. Narita, A.; Wang, X.-Y.; Feng, X.; Müllen, K., New advances in nanographene chemistry. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2015**, *44* (18), 6616-6643.
4. Stepień, M.; Gońka, E.; Żyła, M.; Sprutta, N., Heterocyclic Nanographenes and Other Polycyclic Heteroaromatic Compounds: Synthetic Routes, Properties, and Applications. *Chem. Rev.* **2017**, *117* (4), 3479-3716.
5. Wang, X. Y.; Yao, X.; Narita, A.; Mullen, K., Heteroatom-Doped Nanographenes with Structural Precision. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2019**, *52* (9), 2491-2505.
6. Grzybowski, M.; Sadowski, B.; Butenschon, H.; Gryko, D. T., Synthetic Applications of Oxidative Aromatic Coupling-From Biphenols to Nanographenes. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2020**, *59* (8), 2998-3027.
7. Liu, J.; Feng, X., Synthetic Tailoring of Graphene Nanostructures with Zigzag-Edged Topologies: Progress and Perspectives. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2020**, *59* (52), 23386-23401.
8. Zeng, W.; Wu, J., Open-Shell Graphene Fragments. *Chem* **2021**, *7* (2), 358-386.
9. Guo, X.; Yuan, Z.; Zhu, Y.; Li, Z.; Huang, R.; Xia, Z.; Zhang, W.; Li, Y.; Wang, J., A Nitrogen-Doped Hexapole [7]Helicene versus Its All-Carbon Analogue. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2019**, *58* (47), 16966-16972.
10. Zhu, Y.; Xia, Z.; Cai, Z.; Yuan, Z.; Jiang, N.; Li, T.; Wang, Y.; Guo, X.; Li, Z.; Ma, S.; Zhong, D.; Li, Y.; Wang, J., Synthesis and Characterization of Hexapole [7]Helicene, A Circularly Twisted Chiral Nanographene. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2018**, *140* (12), 4222-4226.

11. Ma, S.; Gu, J.; Lin, C.; Luo, Z.; Zhu, Y.; Wang, J., Supertwistacene: A Helical Graphene Nanoribbon. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2020**, *142* (39), 16887-16893.
12. Cruz, C. M.; Márquez, I. R.; Castro-Fernández, S.; Cuerva, J. M.; Maçõas, E.; Campaña, A. G., A Triskelion-Shaped Saddle-Helix Hybrid Nanographene. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2019**, *58* (24), 8068-8072.
13. Cortizo-Lacalle, D.; Mora-Fuentes, J. P.; Strutyński, K.; Saeki, A.; Melle-Franco, M.; Mateo-Alonso, A., Monodisperse N-Doped Graphene Nanoribbons Reaching 7.7 Nanometers in Length. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2018**, *57* (3), 703-708.
14. Yan, X.; Cui, X.; Li, L.-s., Synthesis of Large, Stable Colloidal Graphene Quantum Dots with Tunable Size. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2010**, *132* (17), 5944-5945.
15. Chen, Y.; Lin, C.; Luo, Z.; Yin, Z.; Shi, H.; Zhu, Y.; Wang, J., Double Pi-Extended Undecabenzol[7]helicene. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2021**, DOI: 10.1002/anie.202014621.
16. Wang, Y.; Yin, Z.; Zhu, Y.; Gu, J.; Li, Y.; Wang, J., Hexapole [9]helicene. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2019**, *58* (2), 587-591.
17. Mora-Fuentes, J. P.; Riaño, A.; Cortizo-Lacalle, D.; Saeki, A.; Melle-Franco, M.; Mateo-Alonso, A., Giant Star-Shaped Nitrogen-Doped Nanographenes. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2019**, *58* (2), 552-556.
18. Beser, U.; Kastler, M.; Maghsoumi, A.; Wagner, M.; Castiglioni, C.; Tommasini, M.; Narita, A.; Feng, X.; Müllen, K., A C216-Nanographene Molecule with Defined Cavity as Extended Coronoid. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138* (13), 4322-4325.
19. Simpson, C. D.; Brand, J. D.; Berresheim, A. J.; Przybilla, L.; Räder, H. J.; Müllen, K., Synthesis of a Giant 222 Carbon Graphite Sheet. *Chem. Eur. J.* **2002**, *8* (6), 1424-1429.
20. Tan, Y.-Z.; Yang, B.; Parvez, K.; Narita, A.; Osella, S.; Beljonne, D.; Feng, X.; Müllen, K., Atomically precise edge chlorination of nanographenes and its application in graphene nanoribbons. *Nat. Commun.* **2013**, *4* (1), 2646.
21. Zhu, Y.; Guo, X.; Li, Y.; Wang, J., Fusing of Seven HBCs toward a Green Nanographene Propeller. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2019**, *141* (13), 5511-5517.
22. Chen, L.; Hernandez, Y.; Feng, X.; Müllen, K., From Nanographene and Graphene Nanoribbons to Graphene Sheets: Chemical Synthesis. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2012**, *51* (31), 7640-7654.
23. Yano, Y.; Mitoma, N.; Ito, H.; Itami, K., A Quest for Structurally Uniform Graphene Nanoribbons: Synthesis, Properties, and Applications. *J. Org. Chem.* **2020**, *85* (1), 4-33.
24. Cai, Z.; Awais, M. A.; Zhang, N.; Yu, L., Exploration of Syntheses and Functions of Higher Ladder-type π -Conjugated Heteroacenes. *Chem* **2018**, *4* (11), 2538-2570.
25. Jolly, A.; Miao, D.; Daigle, M.; Morin, J.-F., Emerging Bottom-Up Strategies for the Synthesis of Graphene Nanoribbons and Related Structures. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2020**, *59* (12), 4624-4633.
26. Peurifoy, S. R.; Sisto, T. J.; Ng, F.; Steigerwald, M. L.; Chen, R.; Nuckolls, C., Dimensional Control in Contorted Aromatic Materials. *Chem. Rev.* **2019**, *19* (6), 1050-1061.
27. Chuvilin, A.; Bichoutskaia, E.; Gimenez-Lopez, M. C.; Chamberlain, T. W.; Rance, G. A.; Kuganathan, N.; Biskupek, J.; Kaiser, U.; Khlobystov, A. N., Self-assembly of a sulphur-terminated graphene nanoribbon within a single-walled carbon nanotube. *Nat. Mater.* **2011**, *10* (9), 687-692.
28. Niu, W.; Liu, J.; Mai, Y.; Müllen, K.; Feng, X., Synthetic Engineering of Graphene Nanoribbons with Excellent Liquid-Phase Processability. *Trends Chem.* **2019**, *1* (6), 549-558.
29. Chen, Z.; Narita, A.; Müllen, K., Graphene Nanoribbons: On-Surface Synthesis and Integration into Electronic Devices. *Adv. Mater.* **2020**, *32* (45), 2001893.
30. Wang, X.-Y.; Narita, A.; Müllen, K., Precision synthesis versus bulk-scale fabrication of graphenes. *Nat. Rev. Chem.* **2017**, *2* (1), 0100.
31. Tsuda, A.; Osuka, A., Fully Conjugated Porphyrin Tapes with Electronic Absorption Bands That Reach into Infrared. *Science* **2001**, *293* (5527), 79-82.
32. Schlicke, B.; Schlüter, A. D.; Hauser, P.; Heinze, J., Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons in the Nanometer Range. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **1997**, *36* (18), 1996-1998.
33. Purushothaman, B.; Bruzek, M.; Parkin, S. R.; Miller, A.-F.; Anthony, J. E., Synthesis and Structural Characterization of Crystalline Nonacenes. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2011**, *50* (31), 7013-7017.
34. Chen, L.; Li, C.; Müllen, K., Beyond perylene diimides: synthesis, assembly and function of higher rylene chromophores. *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2014**, *2* (11), 1938-1956.
35. Liu, J.; Li, B.-W.; Tan, Y.-Z.; Giannakopoulos, A.; Sanchez-Sanchez, C.; Beljonne, D.; Ruffieux, P.; Fasel, R.; Feng, X.; Müllen, K., Toward Cove-Edged Low Band Gap Graphene Nanoribbons. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137* (18), 6097-6103.
36. Ozaki, K.; Kawasumi, K.; Shibata, M.; Ito, H.; Itami, K., One-shot K-region-selective annulative π -extension for nanographene synthesis and functionalization. *Nat. Commun.* **2015**, *6*, 6251.
37. Huang, R.; Phan, H.; Herg, T. S.; Hu, P.; Zeng, W.; Dong, S.-q.; Das, S.; Shen, Y.; Ding, J.; Casanova, D.; Wu, J., Higher Order π -Conjugated Polycyclic Hydrocarbons with Open-Shell Singlet Ground State: Nonazethrene versus Nonacene. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138* (32), 10323-10330.
38. Zeng, W.; Phan, H.; Herg, T. S.; Gopalakrishna, T. Y.; Aratani, N.; Zeng, Z.; Yamada, H.; Ding, J.; Wu, J., Rylene Ribbons with Unusual Diradical Character. *Chem* **2017**, *2* (1), 81-92.
39. Fan, W.; Winands, T.; Doltsinis, N. L.; Li, Y.; Wang, Z., A Decatwistacene with an Overall 170 degrees Torsion. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2017**, *56* (48), 15373-15377.
40. Lee, J.; Li, H.; Kalin, A. J.; Yuan, T.; Wang, C.; Olson, T.; Li, H.; Fang, L., Extended Ladder-Type Benzo[k]tetrathene-Derived Oligomers. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2017**, *56* (44), 13727-13731.
41. Chen, W.; Li, X.; Long, G.; Li, Y.; Ganguly, R.; Zhang, M.; Aratani, N.; Yamada, H.; Liu, M.; Zhang, Q., Pyrene-Containing Twistarene: Twelve Benzene Rings Fused in a Row. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2018**, *57* (41), 13555-13559.
42. Cortizo-Lacalle, D.; Gozalvez, C.; Melle-Franco, M.; Mateo-Alonso, A., A thiadiazole-capped nanoribbon with 18 linearly fused rings. *Nanoscale* **2018**, *10* (24), 11297-11301.
43. Jin, P.; Song, T.; Xiao, J.; Zhang, Q., Recent Progress in Using Pyrene-4,5-diketones and Pyrene-4,5,9,10-tetraketones as Building Blocks to Construct Large Acenes and Heteroacenes. *Asian J. Org. Chem.* **2018**, *7* (11), 2130-2146.
44. Bunz, U. H. F.; Freudenberg, J., N-Heteroacenes and N-Heteroarenes as N-Nanocarbon Segments. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2019**, *52* (6), 1575-1587.
45. Chen, W.; Yu, F.; Xu, Q.; Zhou, G.; Zhang, Q., Recent Progress in High Linearly Fused Polycyclic Conjugated Hydrocarbons (PCHs, $n > 6$) with Well-Defined Structures. *Adv. Sci.* **2020**, *7* (12), 1903766.
46. Liu, G.; Xiao, C.; Negri, F.; Li, Y.; Wang, Z., Dodecatwistarene Imides with Zigzag-Twisted Conformation for Organic Electronics. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2020**, *59* (5), 2008-2012.
47. Castro-Fernández, S.; Cruz, C. M.; Mariz, I. F. A.; Márquez, I. R.; Jiménez, V. G.; Palomino-Ruiz, L.; Cuerva, J. M.; Maçõas, E.; Campaña, A. G., Two-Photon Absorption Enhancement by the Inclusion of a Tropone Ring in Distorted Nanographene Ribbons. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2020**, *59* (18), 7139-7145.
48. Mastalerz, M.; Yang, X.; Rominger, F., Benzo-fused Perylene Oligomers with up to 13 Linearly Annulated Rings. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2021**, DOI: 10.1002/anie.202017062.
49. Chen, F.; Gu, W.; Saeki, A.; Melle-Franco, M.; Mateo-Alonso, A., A Sterically Congested Nitrogenated Benzodipentaphene with a Double π -Expanded Helicene Structure. *Organic Letters* **2020**, *22* (9), 3706-3711.
50. Zhan, X.; Zhang, J.; Tang, S.; Lin, Y.; Zhao, M.; Yang, J.; Zhang, H.-L.; Peng, Q.; Yu, G.; Li, Z., Pyrene fused perylene diimides: synthesis, characterization and applications in organic field-effect transistors and optical limiting with high performance. *Chem. Commun.* **2015**, *51* (33), 7156-7159.
51. Pracht, P.; Bohle, F.; Grimme, S., Automated exploration of the low-energy chemical space with fast quantum chemical methods. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2020**, *22* (14), 7169-7192.
52. Clar, E., *The Aromatic Sextet*. Wiley: London, 1972; pp 17-22.
53. Zhong, Y.; Trinh, M. T.; Chen, R.; Purdum, G. E.; Khlyabich, P. P.; Sezen, M.; Oh, S.; Zhu, H.; Fowler, B.; Zhang, B.; Wang, W.; Nam, C.-Y.; Sfeir, M. Y.; Black, C. T.; Steigerwald, M. L.; Loo, Y.-L.; Ng, F.; Zhu, X. Y.; Nuckolls, C., Molecular helices as electron acceptors in high-performance bulk heterojunction solar cells. *Nat. Commun.* **2015**, *6*, 8242.
54. Zhong, Y.; Sisto, T. J.; Zhang, B.; Miyata, K.; Zhu, X. Y.; Steigerwald, M. L.; Ng, F.; Nuckolls, C., Helical Nanoribbons for Ultra-Narrowband Photodetectors. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2017**, *139* (16), 5644-5647.
55. Sisto, T. J.; Zhong, Y.; Zhang, B.; Trinh, M. T.; Miyata, K.; Zhong, X.; Zhu, X. Y.; Steigerwald, M. L.; Ng, F.; Nuckolls, C., Long, Atomically Precise Donor-Acceptor Cove-Edge Nanoribbons as Electron Acceptors. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2017**, *139* (16), 5648-5651.

56. Ren, T.; Shen, X.; Han, L.; Bai, L.; Zhao, H.; Wu, Y.; Wang, H.; Ba, X., Ladder-Type Perylene Diimides Linked by Pyrene Bridges at Bay Area. *ChemistrySelect* **2016**, *1* (2), 267-271.
57. Birks, J. B.; Birch, D. J. S.; Cordemans, E.; Vander Donckt, E., Fluorescence of the higher helicenes. *Chemical Physics Letters* **1976**, *43* (1), 33-36.

Three molecular nanoribbons are reported. The largest one shows a 53 linearly-fused rings backbone (12.9 nm) and 322 conjugated atoms in its aromatic core ($C_{296}N_{24}S_2$).

